

The Idea of Development: Major Issues and Approaches

Tapas Roy

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.8302555

Abstract

The following article examines the major perspectives of development studies on the basis of the available literature reviews to conceptualize the essential ideas of development. The following shows that there is no central idea of the term development. It is multifaceted and relative term which shifts its ideas across various times and spaces; actors; agencies of development. The article also tried to shown the criticisms has been faces by different perspectives by different discourses of development due to their inherent problems.

Key words: Modernization, Dependency, World System, Socialist, Post Development, Human Development

The idea of development is so complex due to its evolving nature that one cannot bring forth any perfectly satisfactory exposition; though it is one of the central themes of modern social science studies. In human geography socio-economic changes is one of the core areas of studies, particularly the living standards of the human being across the globe. 20th century social science has developed many theories and approaches towards understanding the human engineered development and it is one of the central concerns of the newly emerged countries in the post world war II era. Countries were freed from colonial controls were experiencing new challenges in the form of fulfilling the promises of independence by realizing socio-economic development. In the post-world war era new global super powers took the responsibilities towards determining the paths of development of the underdeveloped countries. Two major theoretical stances have appeared during this period between the race of the capitalist countries and the soviet bloc namely modernization and

socialism. However over the period of time many other theoretical approaches and concepts on development came into being. In the following literature review going to examine the major approaches of development, their primary concerns, scopes and other issues to understand why there is no universal definition of development came into being. What are the parameters that are important to the studies of development.

Studies on development can help us to understand the status and tentative directions towards understanding the essence of the term; broadly speaking development can be understood as the process of socio-economic changes of societies by human efforts. In general terms, "development" means an "event constituting a new stage in a changing situation", (Dictionary.) but its scope is vivid in nature. As Thomas argues, development is 'contested, complex, and ambiguous'. (Thomas, 2000) Gore notes that in the 1950s and 1960s a 'vision of the liberation of people and peoples' dominated, based on 'structural transformation'. (Gore, 2000) The above approaches are not all encompassing story of development studies. The second perspective held the view of the international development donor agencies, where development is directly related to the achievement of poverty reduction and of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). There is a third perspective from a group of writers that Hickey and Mohan (2003: 38) broadly identify as 'post-modernists'. The 'post-modern' position is that 'development' is a 'discourse' (a set of ideas) that actually shapes and frames 'reality' and power relations. It does this because the 'discourse' values certain things over others. For example, those who do not have economic assets are viewed as 'inferior' from a materialistic viewpoint. In terms of 'real development' there might be a new 'discourse' based on 'alternative value systems' which place a much higher value on spiritual or cultural assets, and within which those without significant economic assets would be regarded as having significant wealth. (Hickey & Mohan, 2003)

The emergence of development studies as an academic discipline in the second half of the twentieth century is in large part due to increasing concern about economic prospects for the third world after decolonization. In the immediate post-war period, development economics, a branch of economics, arose out of previous studies in colonial economics. By the 1960s, an increasing number of development economists felt that economics alone could not fully address issues such as political effectiveness and educational provision (Kothari, 2007). Development studies arose as a result of this, initially aiming to integrate ideas of politics and economics. Since then, it has become an increasingly inter- and multi-disciplinary subject, encompassing a variety of social scientific fields (Abbott, 2003). In recent years the use of political economy analysis- the application of the analytical techniques of economics- to try and assess and explain political and social factors that either enhance or limit development has become increasingly widespread as a way of explaining the success or failure of reform processes. The era of modern development is commonly deemed to have commenced with the inauguration speech of Harry S. Truman in 1949. In Point Four of his speech, with reference to Latin America and other poor nations, he said that "for the first time in history, humanity possess[ed] the knowledge and skill to relieve the suffering of these people." But development studies has since also taken an interest in lessons of past development experiences of Western countries. More recently, the emergence of human security – a new, people-oriented approach to understanding and addressing global security threats – has led to a growing recognition of a relationship between security and development. Human security argues that inequalities and insecurity in one state or region have consequences for global security and that it is thus in the interest of all states to address underlying development issues. This relationship with studies of human security is but one example of the interdisciplinary nature of development studies.

Let us examine how the major perspectives of development have tried to understand development

over the period of time. The idea of development was first popularized by modernization perspective, modernization can also be understand as a Eurocentric approach of development, where the capitalist countries known as Global North brought forwarded the idea of development for the Global South like Asia, Africa and Latin America. According to this perspective economic growth is the key index of development and it can be achieved by rapid technological progress in production and making necessary structural changes of the societies. In order to realize the modernization Global north countries extended their support to the Global South Countries in the form of offering debts and technologies; consequently economic growth has been realized by many countries of the world; but not everywhere. In some places like Latin America modernization model of development created further problems. On summing up modernization perspective of development was closely associated with economic growth rather than economic development. As economist Amartya Sen points out, "economic growth is one aspect of the process of economic development." (Sen, 1983) Dependency perspective of development is based upon the criticisms of modernization theory of development; Dos Santos and Rostow ; accordingly the underdevelopment of the poor countries are solely connected with the issue of colonial experience, whereas the advanced countries have their own lines of development history. So it is impossible to make economic development by coping up with the developed countries.

All societies progress through similar stages of development, that today's underdeveloped areas are thus in a similar situation to that of today's developed areas at some time in the past, and that therefore the task in helping the underdeveloped areas out of poverty is to accelerate them along this supposed common path of development, by various means such as investment, technology transfers, and closer integration into the world market.

Dependency theory or dependency theory is a body of social science theories predicated on the

notion that resources flow from a "periphery" of poor and underdeveloped states to a "core" of wealthy states, enriching the latter at the expense of the former. It is a central contention of dependency theory that poor states are impoverished and rich ones enriched by the way poor states are integrated into the "world system."

Dependency theory rejected this view of modernization perspective above, arguing that underdeveloped countries are not merely primitive versions of developed countries, but have unique features and structures of their own; and, importantly, are in the situation of being the weaker members in a world market economy, whereas the developed nations were never in an analogous position; they never had to exist in relation to a bloc of more powerful and economically advanced countries than themselves. Dependency theorists argued, in opposition to free market economists and modernization theorists, that underdeveloped countries needed to reduce their connectedness with the world market so that they can pursue a path more in keeping with their own needs, less dictated by external pressures as, for example, the People's Republic of North Korea has done.

Dependency theory originates with two papers published in 1949 – one by Hans Singer, one by Raúl Prebisch – in which the authors observe that the terms of trade for underdeveloped countries relative to the developed countries had deteriorated over time: the underdeveloped countries were able to purchase fewer and fewer manufactured goods from the developed countries in exchange for a given quantity of their raw materials exports. This idea is known as the Singer-Prebisch thesis. Prebisch, an Argentine economist at the United Nations Commission for Latin America (UNCLA), went on to conclude that the underdeveloped nations must employ some degree of protectionism in trade if they were to enter a self-sustaining development path. He argued that Import-substitution industrialisation (ISI), not a trade-and-export orientation, was the best strategy for underdeveloped countries (James, 1997). The theory

was developed from a Marxian perspective by Paul A. Baran in 1957 with the publication of his *The Political Economy of Growth*. Dependency theory shares many points with earlier, Marxist, theories of imperialism by Rosa Luxemburg and V.I. Lenin, and has attracted continued interest from Marxists. Matias Vernengo, a University of Utah economist, identifies two main streams in dependency theory: the Latin American Structuralist, typified by the work of Prebisch, Celso Furtado and Anibal Pinto at the United Nations Economic Commission for Latin America (ECLAC, or, in Spanish, CEPAL); and the American Marxist, developed by Paul A. Baran, Paul Sweezy, and Andre Gunder Frank¹.

Many of these authors focused their attention on Latin America; the leading dependency theorist in the Islamic world is the Egyptian economist Samir Amin

The theory was popular in the 1960s and 1970s as a criticism of modernization theory (the "stages" hypothesis mentioned above), which was falling increasingly out of favor because of continued widespread poverty in much of the world.

Implications

While there are many different and conflicting ideas on how developing countries can alleviate the effects of the world system, several of the following protectionist/nationalist practices were adopted at one time or another by such countries:

1. Promotion of domestic industry and manufactured goods. By imposing subsidies to protect domestic industries, poor countries can be enabled to sell their own products rather than simply exporting raw materials.
2. Import limitations. By limiting the importation of luxury goods and manufactured goods that can be produced

¹ Short Prebisch biography at Newschool; retrieved July 2009.

within the country, the country can reduce its loss of capital and resources.

3. Forbidding foreign investment. Some governments took steps to keep foreign companies and individuals from owning or operating property that draws on the resources of the country.
4. Nationalization. Some governments have forcibly taken over foreign-owned companies on behalf of the state, in order to keep profits within the country.

World-systems theory (also known as world-systems analysis) is a multidisciplinary, macro-scale approach to world history and social change (Wallerstein, 2004).

World-systems theory stresses that the world-system (and not nation states) should be the basic unit of social analysis. (Wallerstein, 2004). World-system refers to the international division of labor, which divides the world into core countries, semi-periphery countries and the periphery countries. Core countries focus on higher skill, capital-intensive production, and the rest of the world focuses on low-skill, labor-intensive production and extraction of raw materials². This constantly reinforces the dominance of the core countries. Nonetheless, the system is dynamic, and individual states can gain or lose the core (semi-periphery, periphery) status over time.³ For a time, some countries become the world [hegemon](#); throughout last few centuries, this status has passed from the Netherlands, to the United Kingdom and most recently, the United States.

Another major grand theory of development was put forwarded by Immanuel Wallenstein, according to him in order to understand the trajectories of development it has be seen in three tire model

instead of core and peripheral countries. He identified the presence of semi-peripheral countries; where he suggests that it is beneficial for the peripheral countries to do trade and business with semi-peripheral countries to do development instead of core countries.

Conclusion

The above literature review suggests that it is difficult to understand the idea of development with a single definition and particular approach since the issues are vivid in nature. Some of the perspectives are concerned with economic development of the nation's states ignoring the quality of lives; while others have particularly interrogated the consequences of development. Development studies are all about the stories of the approaches and implementation of development programmes has taken so far. Critical understanding of the ideas of development could bring forth better results the future implementations of the programmes.

²

³ Frank Lechner, Globalization theories: World-System Theory, 2001

Bibliography

Abbott, L. F. (2003). *Theories of Industrial Modernization and Enterprise Development: A Review*. ISR/Google Books.

Dictionary., O. E. (n.d.). Retrieved from <http://oxforddictionaries.com>

Gore, C. (2000). The rise and fall of the Washington consensus as a paradigm for developing countries. *28 (5)*, 789–804.

Hickey, S., & Mohan, G. (2003). Relocating Participation within a Radical Politics of Development: Citizenship and Critical Modernism. *'Participation: From Tyranny to Transformation? Exploring new approaches to participation* (pp. 27–28). Manchester: University of Manchester.

James, P. (1997). Post-Dependency: The Third World in an Era of Globalism and Late Capitalism. *Social Transformation and Human Governance Alternatives* , *22 (2)*, pp. 205–226.

Kothari, U. (2007). *A Radical History of Development Studies: Individuals, Institutions and Ideologies for an alternative view*. *The Journal of Peasant Studies* , p. 34/1.

Sen, A. (1983). *Development: Which Way Now?* 93 (372), pp. 745–762.

Thomas, A. (2000). *Development as practice in a liberal capitalist world*. *Journal of International Development* , *12 (6)*, 773–787.

Wallerstein, I. (2004). "World-systems Analysis." *In World System History. In G. Modelski, Encyclopedia of Life Support Systems (EOLSS), Developed under the Auspices of the UNESCO, . Oxford, UK: Eolss Publishers.*